

1 **Supplementary materials and methods**

2 **Primary cultures of sensory neurons**

3 Sensory neurons were extracted from adult mice with 10-15 week-of age (strain:
4 CD57BL/6J). Animals were group housed in a 12-12 light-dark cycle, where the lights were
5 turned on at 8 hours and turned off at 20 hours. Food and water were available ad libitum.
6 Experimental procedures were performed on both male and female mice. Animals were
7 anesthetized by isoflurane and sacrificed by decapitation. The spinal column was excised
8 and the DRGs or TG were extracted, dissected from nerve projections and ganglia were kept
9 in ice-cold Hank's balanced salt solution (HBSS). Ganglia were incubated with collagenase
10 type XI (0.67 mg/mL, Sigma) and dispase type II (3 mg/mL, Gibco) dissolved in INCmix
11 solution (NaCl 155 mM, K₂HPO₄ 1.5 mM, HEPES 5.6 mM, HEPES-Na 4.8 mM, Glucose 5
12 mM - Sigma) at 37°C and 5% CO₂ for 75 minutes. The enzymatic mix solution was then
13 removed, 1 mL of culture medium was added, the tissue was mechanically digested pipetting
14 up to 8 times and supernatant containing digested DRGs was added to a BSA column (15%
15 p/v in PBS, Sigma). The BSA column was centrifuged at 200 g for 7 minutes and decanted,
16 the cell pellet was then diluted in 5 mL of culture medium and centrifuged at 300 g for 7
17 minutes. The exceeding medium was removed, and cells were diluted in complete medium to
18 obtain 3 million cells/mL. MFCs were then seeded adding 5 µL of cell suspension to the
19 somal channel of each chamber. Cultures were incubated in a humidified incubator at 37°C,
20 5% CO₂ for 35 minutes. After this time, 200 µL of complete medium containing murine NGF
21 (mNGF 25s 100 ng/mL, Promega) and human GDNF (hGDNF 100 ng/mL, PeproTech) were
22 added to the somal compartment and 100 µL were added to the axonal compartment.
23 Medium was changed every 48h, decreasing mNGF and hGDNF concentration in the somal
24 compartment, as detailed in Table 1. From day in vitro (DIV) 1, the antimetabolites uridine (17.5
25 µg/mL in water, Sigma) and 5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (7.5 µg/mL in water, Sigma)⁴³ were
26 added to the somal compartment to prevent glial proliferation. For DRGs-keratinocytes co-
27 culture, antimetabolites were not added (Table 2) to the axonal compartment.

28 For the inflammatory model, the culture media is detailed in Table S2. At DIV 5, an
29 inflammatory soup composed of 1 µM bradykinin, 10 µM PGE-2, 10 µM histamine, 10 µM
30 serotonin and 15 µM ATP was added to the axonal chamber for 24h. Functional
31 measurements were performed upon removal of the inflammatory soup at DIV6
32 (sensitization) or at DIV8 (resolution).

33 For the chemotherapy-induced peripheral neuropathy model (CIPN) model, the culture
34 medium is in Table S3. At DIV5, 1 µM paclitaxel was added to the soma compartment for
35 24h in the presence of 5% FBS, 5 mg/mL NaCl and additional B27 as described in Table S3.
36 Functional measurements were performed 48h (DIV8, sensitization) and 96h (DIV10,
37 resolution) upon removal of paclitaxel, as described²⁸.

38 Media were changed using two micropipettes at the same time and pipetting not more than
39 50 µL, in order to minimize shear stress. Furthermore, to reduce media evaporation, MFCs
40 were put in a 100 mm petri dish with a 35 mm petri dish filled with sterile dH₂O.

41 For DRGs cultures, 4 mice were used (2 males and 2 females) resulting in ≥2 coverslips per
42 animal and analysing 5,498 neurons. For DRGs microfluidic cultures, 4 animals were used (2
43 males and 2 females) resulting in minimum of 2 MFC per animal with a total number of
44 crossing neurons=747. For DRGs-keratinocytes co-culture 4 animals were used (2 males
45 and 2 females), resulting in 2 MFC per animal with a total number of crossing neurons=298.
46 For CIPN model 6 animals were used (3 males and 3 females) resulting in a minimum of 3
47 MFC per animal with a total number of crossing neurons=3,018. For the inflammatory model,
48 5 animals were used (3 males and 2 females) resulting in a minimum of 2 MFC per animal
49 were cultured with total number of crossing neurons=1,638. For TG MFC culture 4 mice were
50 used, (2 males and 2 females) with a minimum of 2 MFC per animal were cultured, with a
51 total number of crossing neurons= 740.

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1 **Microfluidic chambers**

2 24 mmx60 mm coverslips were put under UV light on both sides for 30 minutes each. The
3 assays presented in this work were performed using Millipore devices "AXIS™: Axon
4 Investigation System" in the design AX150, that consists of 4 microwells of 8 mm diameter
5 each, 2 microchannels of 1,5 mm length that are interconnected by approximately 120
6 microgrooves. Cleaned chambers were sterilized with filtered 70% ethanol for 5 minutes,
7 washed three times with filtered milli-Q sterile water and then dried up under a hood⁴⁴.
8 Coverslips were coated with poly-L-lysine solution (0.01%, Sigma) and then incubated at
9 37°C overnight. The following day, the coverslips were washed three times with milli-Q sterile
10 water and dried thoroughly. Microfluidic chambers were placed with microgroove side faced
11 down onto the coverslips and gently pressed down to ensure a tightly sealing. 200 µL of
12 laminin (20 µg/ml in Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), Sigma) were added to
13 each well of the somal compartment and 100µL of laminin were added to each well of the
14 axonal compartment. The chambers were then incubated overnight at 37°C to allow laminin
15 to fill the microchannels.

16 **Morphological analysis**

17 Mouse DRGs axons were stained with the fluorescent tracer 1,1'-Dioctadecyl-3,3,3',3'-
18 Tetramethylindocarbocyanine (DiD', 1:200, Invitrogen) and photos of the axonal
19 compartment at different DIVs were taken with inverted microscope (Axiovert 200, Carl
20 Zeiss) with a 10X air objective. Axons were selected in ImageJ - Confocal Uniovi 1-15 and
21 length was calculated. Raw measurements of axonal length during DIVs were graphed with
22 GraphPad Prism 9 to obtain length distribution.

23 **Keratinocytes culture and co-culture with sensory neurons**

24 HaCaT (CLS-Cell Line Services) were maintained in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium
25 (DMEM) GlutaMAX (Gibco) with 10% FBS (Gibco), 1% penicillin/streptomycin (10000 U/mL,
26 Gibco) at 37°C with 5% CO₂. Cells were serially passaged at 70-90% confluence. At DIV 1 of
27 DRGs culture, the keratinocytes were trypsinized and counted with a Neubauer chamber.
28 After drying up the lower microchannel, 20 µL of cells were seeded at 2 million cell/mL to
29 obtain a 90-100% confluence at DIV 6, when calcium imaging assays were performed. 60
30 minutes after seeding, medium was added to the axonal wells. The medium for
31 keratinocytes-axons co-culture was HaCaT maintaining medium supplemented with mNGF
32 25s (100 ng/mL, Promega) and hGDNF (100 ng/mL, PeproTech), in order to create a
33 neurotrophic gradient between compartments to allow axonal outgrowth. The medium was
34 changed every two days as for DRGs microfluidic culture (Table S1).

35 **Calcium imaging**

36 At DIV 5, the fluorescent tracer DiD' (1:200, Invitrogen) was added to the axonal
37 compartment and allowed to be taken overnight by crossing neurons. The following day, both
38 microfluidic chambers compartments were washed twice with imaging buffer consisting of
39 NaCl 140 mM, HEPES 10 mM, KCl 4 mM, CaCl₂ 1.8 mM, MgCl₂ 1 mM (Sigma), D-glucose 5
40 mM (VWR|BDH Prolabo Chemicals), pH 7.4. Afterwards, neurons in the somal compartment
41 were loaded with Fluo-4 AM (5 µM, Molecular Probes, Invitrogen) and pluronic acid (0.02%
42 p/v, Molecular Probes, Invitrogen) for 1 hour at 37°C in imaging buffer, followed by a 20 min
43 wash. During the assay, additional caution was taken to maintain compartments isolated.
44 The experiments were performed on an inverted microscope (Axiovert 200, ZEISS)
45 comprising of the ORCA Flash LT camera (Hamamatsu Photonics) and images were
46 processed with HC Image package software (Hamamatsu Photonics) and analysis software
47 (AquaCosmos Ratio Imaging Software, Hamamatsu Photonics). Fluorescence was
48 monitored through a 10x air objective. First, bright field and DiD' staining in the soma were
49 visualized and only neurons exhibiting DiD' staining were chosen for analysis (Fig. S1). DiD'
50 was excited at 649 nm and emitted fluorescence was filtered at 668 nm. Regions of interest
51 were drawn around loaded cell soma and then transposed to Fluo-4 image. Fluo-4-AM was
52 excited at 500 nm with an exposure time of 200 ms and emitted fluorescence filtered at 535

1 nm (Lambda-10-2-filter wheel, Sutter Instruments) and one Fluo-4 image every 3 seconds
2 was taken. The axonal compartment was stimulated with capsaicin (100 nM, Sigma),
3 menthol (100 μ M, Sigma), allyl isothiocyanate (AITC, 100 μ M, Sigma) and KCl (40 mM,
4 Sigma) (NaCl 140 mM, HEPES 10 mM, KCl 40 mM, CaCl₂ 1.8 mM, MgCl₂ 1 mM (Sigma), D-
5 glucose 5 mM, pH 7.4). Capsaicin, menthol and AITC were dissolved in dimethyl sulphoxide
6 (DMSO) (Sigma) and then diluted in imaging buffer to have a final DMSO concentration of
7 0.01% v/v. Finally, the soma was stimulated with 40 mM KCl. Perfusion was performed with
8 a peristaltic pump (PPS2, Multichannel System) at 0.2-0.4 mL/min perfusion (depending on
9 how permissive the microfluidic chamber was to the passage of liquid) and 5 mL/min suction.
10 Each drug application was separated by a 4-5 min wash with imaging buffer. Analysis of
11 percentage of cells responding to each stimulus was performed considering crossing
12 neurons (Did' and KCl positive) as the total number of cells. The soma KCl response was
13 considered as the maximal Ca²⁺ signal and was used to normalize the size of the responses.
14 An increase in fluorescence was considered a response if it was higher than 10 times the
15 noise of the baseline before adding the stimuli to the axonal compartment or 20 times before
16 the addition of 40 mM KCl in the soma compartment.

17 **RTqPCR in microfluidic culture**

18 Soma and axons were collected separately by pipetting and centrifuged at 13.000 RPM for 5
19 minutes. Supernatant was discarded and the cell pellet was stored at -80°C or RNA was
20 immediately extracted with E.Z.N.A.® MicroElute Total RNA Kit (Omega Bio-Tek). RNA was
21 then retro-transcribed with First strand cDNA Synthesis Kit (ThermoFisher) to cDNA, using
22 dT primers in order to retro-transcribe mRNA only (Table S8). Quantitative PCR was
23 performed using PowerUp SYBR Green Master Mix (AppliedBiosystems). SYBR Green PCR
24 was performed using QuantStudio 3 thermocycler (Applied Biosystems), with the following
25 protocol: 50°C 2', 95°C 2', 95°C 15s, 60°C 1' for 40 cycles. Data were normalized to GAPDH
26 and represented as relative expression 2^(-ΔCt).

27 **Multielectrode array in microfluidic culture**

28 Electrophysiological recordings were performed using multiple electrode planar arrays of 60-
29 electrode MEA chips, with 30 μ m diameter electrodes and 200 μ m inter-electrode spacing
30 with an integrated reference electrode (Multichannel Systems). MEA plates were treated with
31 poly-d-lysine 0,1 mg/mL and laminin 20 μ g/mL and coupled to MFC to have the soma
32 compartment on top of the electrodes. Mouse DRGs were then seeded in the soma
33 compartment and at DIV 6 MEA was performed stimulating axons with capsaicin (200 nM),
34 menthol (100 μ M) and AITC (100 μ M). Afterwards, soma depolarization was elicited with 40
35 mM KCl as a positive control.

36 **MTT assay**

37 HaCaT were seeded in a 96 well plate (Corning) at 40,000 cell/mL. The following day, cells
38 were treated with compounds present in the DRG culture medium (Table 1): mNGF 25s (100
39 ng/mL, Promega), hGDNF (100 ng/mL, PeproTech), uridine (17.5 μ g/mL, Sigma) and with 5-
40 fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine (7.5 μ g/mL). As positive viability control, cells were left untreated. As
41 negative viability control, cells were treated with DMSO 10% for 24h. After 5-days exposure,
42 the cells were incubated with MTT (0.25 mg/mL, Sigma) for 3h at 37°C. Absorbance at 570
43 nm was measured with PolarStar plate reader (BMG Labtech).

44 **Axonal density estimation.**

45 Mouse DRGs were cultured in MFC, and at DIV 5, nerve endings were treated with
46 the inflammatory mediators listed in Table S2 or their vehicle (H₂O), or with 1 μ M
47 paclitaxel or its vehicle (DMSO 0.04%) for 24 hours. To monitor the axonal density,
48 neurons were loaded with Calcein AM (Sigma) at a concentration of 2.5 μ M for 1
49 hour at 37°C. Fluorescence intensity of the soma and axonal compartments were
50 imaged before treatments (DIV5) and post-treatments (as indicated) using a
51 fluorescence microscope (Axioserver) with a 20x long distance objective. Axonal

- 1 fluorescence post-treatment (arbitrary units) was quantified and normalized with
- 2 respect to that of pretreatment (DIV 5) to obtain a measurement of axonal density.

1 **Supplementary figures**

2

3 **Figure S1. RT-qPCR of mRNA from soma or axons** retrieved from mouse DRGs cultured
4 in microfluidic chambers during 6 DIV or from total mouse DRGs tissue. N=3 mice. Data
5 represented as mean \pm SEM.

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